

A New Fuzzy Kohonen Clustering Network Based on Histogram For Image Segmentation

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Abstract- In this study, Fuzzy Kohonen Clustering Networks (FKCN) algorithm is proposed for image segmentation. But this algorithm for iterative operation will take very long time. Therefore, care has been taken in order to make the FKCN algorithm realistically useful for image segmentation. In this work, a new FKCN algorithm has been developed which based on image histogram. Theoretical analysis and experimental results show that computing time decreased and proposed FKCN was successful algorithm for image segmentation.

Keywords : Kohonen Clustering Network, Fuzzy C-means, Image Segmentation.

1. Introduction

Image segmentation is the most basic and important technique in image processing. The task of segmentation is to partition an image into several meaningful areas according to some characteristic, gray level, color, and so on. The characteristics will be the same or very similar in the inner of those areas and distinct in other areas. Essentially, image segmentation is a classification procedure based on the properties of the pixels concerned [1]. In a automatic pattern recognition system, the input will be scenic information and the output should be the correct interpretation for such scene. Usually, a scenic image is very complicated and varied, therefore, many pixels will be uncertain which clusters in area they should exactly belong to. In this case, interpretation of a scene can only be in the sense of fuzzy.

The area of classical pattern recognition most closely related to the Kohonen self-organizing algorithms is known as cluster analysis. Clustering algorithms attempt to assess the interaction among patterns by organizing the patterns into clusters such that patterns within a cluster are more similar to each other than patterns belonging to different clusters. Treatments of many classical approaches to this problem include the texts by Kohonen, Bezdek, Duda and Hart, Tou and Gonzalez [2, 3, 4].

In this work, it has been attempted to make FKCN algorithm which introduced by Bezdek and Pal [5], realistically useful for image segmentation. Proposed algorithm keeps the advantage of using Fuzzy Kohonen Clustering Networks (FKCN) algorithm and furthermore it reduces computational time using image histogram information. First of all, clusters on histogram are determined. Secondly, every pixel in the image is assigned a cluster membership value. Using these membership values, every pixel is classified into clusters. These clusters correspond to segments in original image.

2. Fuzzy Kohonen Clustering Network

Kohonen Clustering Networks (KCN) are unsupervised schemes which find the best set of weights for hard clusters in an iterative. The structure of KCN consists of two layers: an input (input) layer, and output (competitive) layer as shown in Fig. 1. Each output node has a prototype or weight vector attached to it, and it is this network vector that is adjusted during learning. Given an input vector, the neurons in the output layer compete among themselves and the winner (whose weight has the minimum distance from the input) updates its weights and those of some set of predefined neighbors. The process is continued until the weight vectors stabilize. In this method, a learning rate must be defined which decreases with time in order to force termination.

Figure 1. Kohonen Clustering Network, KCN

However, Kohonen Clustering Networks (KCNs) suffer from several major problems. KCN are heuristic procedures, so termination is not based on optimizing any model of the process or its data. KCN clustering is closely related to the Fuzzy C-means (FCM) algorithms. Fuzzy C-means algorithms are optimization produces [6], whereas KCN is not, integration of FCM and KCN is one way to address several problems of KCNs. Huntshberger and Aggarwal [7] first considered this approach. Tsao, Bezdek and Pal extend their ideas to a new family of algorithms called the Fuzzy Kohonen Clustering Network (FKCN) algorithms. They combine the ideas of fuzzy membership values for learning rates, the parallelism of fuzzy C-means and update rules of KCNs. FKCN is self-organizing, since the "size" of the update neighborhood is automatically adjusted during learning, and FKCN usually terminates in such a way that the FCM objective function is approximately minimized. Kohonen clustering network uses following update rule:

$$V_{i,k} = V_{i,k-1} + \alpha_{i,k} (X_k - V_{i,k-1}) \quad (1)$$

Where $V_{i,k}$ the cluster center for subset i in feature space; $\alpha_{i,k}$ is learning rate, X_k is data k .

Recent studies have shown a close relationship between numerical results generated by KCN and FCM. Huntshberger and Aggarwal proposed the following KCN update rule:

$$V_{i,k} = V_{i,k-1} + U_{i,k} (X_k - V_{i,k-1}) \quad (2)$$

where $U_{i,k}$ is calculated in this form

$$U_{i,k} = \frac{V_{i,k} - V_{i,k-1}}{\sum_{k=1}^n (V_{i,k} - V_{i,k-1})}$$

and $V_{i,k}$ the cluster center for subset i in feature space; $U_{i,k}$ the fuzzy membership value of

pixel k in cluster i ; X_k show pixel k , $k=1, \dots, n$. Tsao, Bezdek and Pal complete integration of FCM and KCN by defining the learning rate for Kohonen updating as

$$\alpha_{i,k,t} = \left(\frac{U_{i,k,t}}{m_i} \right)^m \quad m_i = \frac{(m_i - 1)}{t \cdot \max} \quad (3)$$

Where $U_{i,k,t}$ is calculated from above equation, but $m_i = m_i - (m_i - 1)$, here m_i some positive constant greater than one, and $m_i \rightarrow 1$. In practice, t cannot go to infinity, so we put $Am = (m_i - 1) / \max$, where $\max$ is the iteration limit for fuzzy KCN (FKCN). Fuzzy Kohonen Clustering Network Algorithm is shown as follows:

- Step 1. Fix $C, ||*||$ and $\epsilon > 0$ some small positive constant.
- Step 2. Initialize $V_0 = (V_{1,0}, V_{2,0}, \dots, V_{c,0})$. Choose $m_i > 0$ and $\max = \text{iterate limit}$.
- Step 3. For $t = 1, 2, \dots, \max$
 - (a) Compute all (cn) learning rates $\{\alpha_{i,k,t}\}$ with Eqn (3)
 - (b) Update all (c) weight vectors $\{V_{i,t}\}$ with

$$V_{i,t} = V_{i,t-1} + \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k,t} (X_k - V_{i,t-1})}{\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k,t}} \quad (4)$$

- (c) Compute $E_t = ||V_t - V_{t-1}||$,
- (d) If $E_t < \epsilon$ stop, else $t = t + 1$ goto step 3.

3. Proposed Histogram Based Formulation

In this work, FKCN is examined and its application to segmentation problem is considered. In most applications, image size is so large. Therefore, for large amounts of data, the computation of iterative FKCN algorithm takes long computational time. In this proposed algorithm, in order to overcome time problem, image histogram is used for this source of information. New algorithm uses gray level to replace the gray function in image space for the data item n .

In the following discussion, we refer to the algorithm as histogram approach. The non-negative set $G = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, L-1\}$ is defined as gray level. For image size $M \times N$, at point (i, j) , $f(i, j)$ is gray level, $i = 1, \dots, M$, $j = 1, \dots, N$. Use $h(k)$ to denote the number of pixels having gray level k , $k = 1, 2, \dots, L-1$. Where $h(k)$ is called histogram. In the histogram based FKCN algorithm, the following equation is developed to calculate the cluster center in gray level:

$$V_{i,t} = V_{i,t-1} + \frac{\sum_{k=1}^L \alpha_{i,k,t} (k - V_{i,t-1}) h(k)}{\sum_{k=1}^L \alpha_{i,k,t} h(k)} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, a new algorithm is proposed to produce image segmentation. The computing procedures are very similar to those described above. Here it can be seen that the number of data set has been reduced from originally $M \times N$ to 1 after introducing the histogram. Start with properties. For an image of 256×256 size and of 8-bit gray level (or 1-256), the number of computing time will approximately improve $256 \times 256 = 256^2 = 256$ times if we do not spend all the time for calculating the histogram.

2. Fuzzy Kohonen Clustering Network

Kohonen Clustering Networks (KCN) are unsupervised schemes which find the best set of weights for hard clusters in an iterative. The structure of KCN consists of two layers, an input (fanout) layer and output (competitive) layer as shown in Fig. 1. Each output node has a prototype or weight vector attached to it, and it is this network vector that is adjusted during learning. Given an input vector, the neurons in the output layer compete among themselves and the winner (whose weight has the minimum distance from the input) updates its weights and those of some set of predefined neighbors. The process is continued until the weight vectors stabilize. In this method, a learning rate must be defined which decreases with time in order to force termination.

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$$V_{i,k,t} = V_{i,k,t-1} + \alpha_{i,k,t} \cdot (X_{i,k} - V_{i,k,t-1}) \quad (1)$$

Where $V_{i,k}$ the cluster center for subset i in feature space; $\alpha_{i,k}$ is learning rate, $X_{i,k}$ is data k . Recent studies have shown a close relationship between numerical results generated by KCN and FCM. Huntsberger and Ajmanangsee proposed the following KCN update rule:

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where $U_{i,k}$ is calculated in this form

$$U_{i,k} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m \left(\frac{X_{i,k} - V_{j,k}}{\|X_{i,k} - V_{j,k}\|} \right)^2}{\sum_{j=1}^m \left(\frac{X_{i,k} - V_{j,k}}{\|X_{i,k} - V_{j,k}\|} \right)^2}$$

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Where $U_{i,k}$ is calculated from above equation, but $m_i = m_i - 1$, here m_i some positive constant greater than one, and $m_i \rightarrow 1$. In practice, t cannot go to infinity, so we put $\Delta m = (m_i - 1) / \text{tmax}$, where tmax is the iteration limit for fuzzy KCN (FKCN). Fuzzy Kohonen Clustering Network Algorithm is shown as follows:

- Step 1. Fix C, ϵ, ϵ and $\epsilon > 0$ some small positive constant.
- Step 2. Initialize $V_{i,k} = (V_{i,1}, V_{i,2}, \dots, V_{i,n})$, Choose $m_i > 0$ and $\text{tmax} = \text{iterate limit}$.
- Step 3. For $t=1, 2, \dots, \text{tmax}+1$
 - (a) Compute all (cn) learning rates $\{\alpha_{i,k,t}\}$ with Eqn.(3)
 - (b) Update all (cn) weight vectors $\{V_{i,k,t}\}$ with

$$V_{i,k,t} = V_{i,k,t-1} + \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k,t} (X_{i,k} - V_{i,k,t-1})}{\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_{i,k,t}} \quad (4)$$

- (c) Compute $E_t = \|V_{i,t} - V_{i,t-1}\|$,
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$$V_{i,k} = V_{i,k,t-1} + \frac{\sum_{k=1}^L \alpha_{i,k,t} (k - V_{i,k,t-1}) h(k)}{\sum_{k=1}^L \alpha_{i,k,t} h(k)} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, a new algorithm is proposed to produce image segmentation. The computing procedures are very similar to those described above. Here it can be seen that the number of data set has been reduced from originally $M \times N$ to 1 after introducing the histogram statistical property. For an image of 256×256 size and of 8-bit gray level (or $L=256$), the amount of computing time will approximately improve $256 \times 256 = 256$ times if we do not consider the time for calculating the histogram.

4. Conclusions

In this study, using image histogram information, FKCN is supplied with the feature of image segmentation. Proposed algorithm determines cluster membership values in a short time successfully. Furthermore, proposed network can work with more than two segments, the constant C in the algorithm corresponds to number of clusters, therefore number of segments in the original image. The proposed algorithm was applied to various images and shown that it can reduce the computing time significantly. The segmented images for this new algorithm are shown Figs.2-4.

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Figure 2, (a) Original House image (b) for two cluster (c=2) segmented image and (c) for three (c=3) segmented image with histogram based FKCN.

Figure 3, (a) Original Leima image (b) for two cluster (c=2) segmented image and (c) for five (c=5) segmented image with histogram based FKCN.

Figure 4, (a) Original Cameraman image (b) for two cluster (c=2) segmented image and (c) for three (c=3) segmented image with histogram based FKCN.

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